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GENERAL INFORMATION

Congress dates

19-21 October 2018/ Sarajevo, B&H
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Language

The official language of the ICCCEB&H 2018 is English

Venue and Registration

Hotel Holiday, Zmaja od Bosne 4, Sarajevo

Registration desk will be open on 19 October 2018 Friday from 8:00 till 17:00 and on 20 October 2018 Saturday from 8:30 till 12:00

KEY TO ABSTRACT IDENTIFICATION

PL	Plenary lecture
OP	Oral presentation
PP-AC	Poster presentation - Analytical Chemistry
PP-IC	Poster presentation - Inorganic Chemistry
PP-BB	Poster presentation - Biochemistry and Biotechnology
PP-PHC	Poster presentation – Phytochemistry
PP-CAM	Poster presentation –Chemistry of Advanced Materials
PP-ENC	Poster presentation – Environmental Chemistry
PP-EDC	Poster presentation – Education in Chemistry
PP-CE	Poster presentation – Chemical Engineering
PP-PTC	Poster presentation – Physical and Theretical Chemistry
PP-OMC	Poster presentation – Organic and Medicinal Chemistry
PP-RC	Poster presentation – Radiochemistry
PP-TRC	Poster presentation – Topics related to Chemistry

Polyphenols from Merlot Wine as Antiinflammatory and Neuroprotective Agents

**Majkić, T.^a, Torović, Lj.^b, Svirčev, E.^a, Simin, N.^a, Šibul, F.^a, Orčić, D.^a,
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Abstract: The aim of this study was to evaluate the phenolic composition and biological activity of four samples of Merlot wines. In order to thoroughly evaluate the phenolic profile of investigated samples, an LC-MS/MS technique was applied to evaluate the quantitative content of 47 phenolics, followed by HPLC-UV/VIS technique for detection of 5 anthocyanins. Among 28 detected phenolics, dominant compounds were malvidin-3-*O*-glucoside, gallic acid, and catechin. Antiinflammatory activity was determined as a potential to inhibit production of prostaglandin E₂ and thromboxane A₂. Macrophages (derived from U937 monocytes) were pretreated with wine samples and inflammation was induced by LPS. Quantification of produced eicosanoids in cell lysate was done by LS-MS/MS. Neuroprotective effect was estimated through a potential of acetylcholinesterase inhibition. All analyzed samples showed moderate antiinflammatory potential. Concerning the neuroprotective effect, samples exhibited modest activity in comparison with physostigmine, a well-known acetylcholinesterase inhibitor. Some correlation between phenolic profile and biological activities of examined samples was noticed. Obtained results support further utilization of Merlot grapes and wine as agents with valuable biological activities. Moreover, they indicate that polyphenolic compounds from Merlot wine could positively affect some pathological processes associated with inflammation, such as atherosclerosis.

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